

Ensemble Classifier Model for Soil Health Data Farmer's Decision Support System

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Abstract— Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy with 18 % of GDP and 40% of NDP contribution. Indian Farmers are loaded with enormous difficulties even for their livelihood. Production in rural India is extremely low due to unscientific farming practices, fragmented land holdings, lack of agro-climatic focus for crop selection, lack of access to the right farming advice at the right time. The major challenges faced in agriculture are Crop mapping, yield prediction, quality of food produced, Sustainable water management, variable rate fertilizer, variable rate pesticide. This paper focuses on the major challenge of crop-soil mapping. Soil fertility plays an important role in maintaining crop growth and increase the production. Based on micro-macro nutrient content, pH value, EC value present in the soil, the suitable crop is identified. Ensemble machine learning classifier algorithms are used to develop a novel soil health analyser and crop recommendation system for Madurai District .Design of Smart Information System (DSIS) application has been developed to serve the farmers upon request. The performance of proposed model is analyzed and it is compared with the existing classification model for agricultural data.

Keywords— Agriculture, Ensemble classifier, Classification, Data Driven Decision, Crop Selection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy. Over 70% of Tamilnadu's population depends on agricultural sources for their income. According to Federation of Tamil Nadu Agricultural Associations census, about 9 Lakhs farmers have stopped agriculture due to huge loss, unpredictable climatic support, unfamiliarised scientific practices, large input costs. Though many of the developed and developing countries are practicing precision agriculture widely, small land hold agriculturists face huge challenges in adopting such practices due to literacy as well as unawareness in India. Soil management, crop management, water management, disease/pest management and waste management are important management that contributes to healthy and sustainable agriculture. Soil is the major decision maker of farmer's income. Hence Soil Management plays a vital role in agriculture. The National Soil Survey Center defined soil as "a living, dynamic resource that supports plant life. It is composed of different size mineral particles, organic matter, and numerous species of living organisms. Soil has biological, chemical, and physical properties that are always changing" (National Soil Survey Center, 1996, p. 1). Soil fertility is the capacity of soil to supply essential nutrients to crops. It is the most critical element for crop production and maintenance. Fertility level of soil is the predominant deciding factor of crop yield. Soil fertility level depends on major parameters such as PH value, N, P, K, Mn, B, EC; OC. Soil management i.e. classification of soil based on its compositing parameters is an important problem which when addressed with computing advancements can help many farmers. With the availability of large field level data collection, data mining approach can

significantly devise a solution for soil fertility problem. Soil fertility classification based on its physical and chemical compositions was the focus of this paper. Building a data model to predict soil fertility using data mining approach was the proposed solution. When the level of fertility is identified, the farmer can decide the appropriate crop to cultivate and system also provides the fertilizer to be used. Soil health data of Madurai region consisting of 20,000 instances with 13 attributes was the target data collected from <https://soil-health.dac.gov.in/>

2. MOTIVATION

Indian economy holds greater promise on agriculture. Though many technological advancements changes the world around us, farming and farmers are facing life challenges still. To support small and marginal landholding farmers in making right decision of cultivating crop based on fertility level is the focus. This information shall be used by the farmers for choosing of crops, quantity of fertilizer requirement and proper conservation of soil fertility. Data asset controls and rules the entire world economy market. Taking advantage of the data asset in relation with soil fertility, a data mining approach is used to build a data model to predict the soil fertility level.

The main three challenges of the society

1. Feeding a growing population,
2. Providing a livelihood for farmers,
3. Protecting the environment can be tackled by addressing the soil management problem.

3. BACKGROUND WORK

By definition, Data mining is the practice of examining large pre-existing databases in order to generate new information. Many researchers has contributed to agricultural data analysis and helps to fit in following problems

1. Grading food quality – Like Mushroom grading
2. Estimation of Damage caused by pest
3. Crop yield estimation
4. Influence of climate on crop yield

Soil constitutes many nutrients with varying levels. Soil fertility is the preliminary factor of crop yield. In Reference [1] – researchers believe that nutritional disorders can be determined by evaluating the fertility status of the soils significantly. Hence, a detailed study of micro and macro nutrients in some soils of Senapati district, Manipur, India was conducted. The availability of nutrients, its mean and range, relationship between each existing nutrients and its distribution is also analysed using simple correlation coefficient effectively. Major chemical components that contributes to crop yield are macro nutrients such as N,P, K. Distribution of micro nutrients such as Zn, Cu, Mn, Fe and B were influenced positively by pH, EC and organic carbon content of the soil . The nature of the soils was predominately strongly acidic to neutral in the focused area and highly influenced by the climatic conditions of the district (high rainfall).

Applying Data mining techniques to soil data can generate reports to facilitate decision support regarding crop rotation, fertilizer requirements and harvesting procedures [2]. The experiment in [2] is carried out with soil survey data (120 soil testing samples) collected from Telangana & Andhra-Pradesh states. To group the soil based on the chemical components, region based Cluster Analysis of soil is performed using k-mean clustering technique. 5 variants of clusters are formed as 15% of salinity, 6% In-Humus, 21% Alkaline, 25% Major-low, 21% Minor-low and 29% Secondary-low lands were formed. To these cluster data, apriori association rule mining technique is applied which resulted in interesting rules with best crop nutrients requirement. Frequent Item sets obtained is used to assist farmers to improve farm productivity by providing crop rotating scheme.

The prediction of pH levels is important to know the nutrients availability in the soil [3]. Classification algorithms like Logistic Regression (LR), Bernoulli Naïve Bayes (BNB), Decision Tree (DT), Extra Tree (ET), Random Forest (RF) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) are used to evaluate and predict the pH values. The Study determined that the performance of the DT and RF model for pH prediction is high compared to the other algorithms in terms of accuracy. The classifiers performance has improved by possessing feature scaling techniques like normalization and standardization.

Prediction of soil fertility level to facilitate the estimation of fertility level and suggests the suitable crop for sowing using C5.0: ADT Classifier algorithm has been proposed. Rajeswari et.al[4] considered soil testing dataset with 12 attributes such as pH, EC, OC, N, P, K, S, Zn, B, Ca, Fertility level and 20,000 instances. Chi-square Map Reduce feature selection technique was used to check the dependency between the target variable and the feature considered. In order to address the data size problem with data mining algorithms Map Reduce concept was used. As a novelty, Pruning technique was introduced between map phase and reduce phase technique downsize the decision tree and thus instance classification becomes easier. The proposed model showed 5% increase in accuracy than existing method.

Priyadharshini A [5] examined various machine learning algorithms in her research. Her work demonstrates how this technology can help mitigate crop failure and improve productivity by assisting farmers in selecting the right crops and offering insights that typical data might not cover. Among the different algorithms tested, the neural network proved to be the most precise.

The crop recommendation system proposed by Pudumalar et al [6] focuses on enhancing precision agriculture through machine learning. This system utilizes an ensemble model with a majority voting technique to integrate various machine learning algorithms. The goal is to aid farmers in selecting the most suitable crops by analyzing diverse factors such as soil properties, weather conditions, and historical yield data. The model aims to improve crop yield predictions and optimize agricultural productivity by providing tailored recommendations based on these inputs.

[7] explores enhancing crop recommendation systems through ensemble learning techniques. The primary focus is on integrating multiple machine learning models to improve prediction accuracy and reliability for crop selection in precision agriculture. The study utilizes ensemble methods such as bagging and boosting. These techniques aggregate predictions from various base models to reduce errors and increase the robustness of the crop recommendations.

More relevant information to make critical farming decisions is identified as environmental conditions, soil and climatic data, input levels [7]. The accurate yield estimation is

an important issue in the agriculture planning. Information Environmental conditions, variability in soil, input levels for farmers to use information and get help to make critical farming decisions and commodity prices have made it all the more relevant for farmers to use information.

Research Questions

The motivation for research is supported by the following research questions:

RQ1: Does categorization of soils based on chemical composition help the farmers to decide on sowing appropriate crops. What is the impact of implementing technology based decisions in agriculture domain?

RQ2: Does data driven farming promote sustainable agriculture?

STUDY AREA AND DATASET

Madurai district is located in southern part of Tamil Nadu, India. It covers an area of 3741.73 Km² including Madurai city as the only urbanized area and Melur, Thirumangalam, Vadipatti, Alanganallur, Usilampatti, Kallupatti, Peraiyur and Kottampatti as the rural areas of the district. Topographically, the north and western portions are uplands whereas south and eastern portions of the district are plains. It has peculiar terrestrial land use with good agriculture practice and urban settlements which are located on the part of Vaigai river basin. The climate of Tamil Nadu is tropical in nature with little variation in summer and winter temperatures. The average annual rainfall in this area ranges between 635 and 884 mm per year [6]. It lies between the latitude longitudes coordinates of 9°55'2.46"N, 78°7'10.63"E as shown in figure-1.

Fig.1. Location of Study area

Soil health data of Madurai region of about 13 blocks consisting of 20,000 instances with 14 attributes was the target data collected from <https://soilhealth.dac.gov.in>. Dataset attributes and its necessity are described in Table 1.

Attribute	Necessity
Village name	Sample location
pH	Measure of acidity or alkalinity of the soil.
EC	Measure of salinity of the soil
OC	Measure of organic matter in the soil, heart for soil fertility.
N	Acts as Building block of proteins, nucleic acids
P	helps in growth of new tissue and division of cells.
K	plays an essential role in photosynthesis and metabolism of plants
S, Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn, Ca, B	Micronutrients
Fertility Status	Low, Medium, High

Table 1. Soil dataset attributes

5. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

In this proposed work, a fresh hand well-designed model is used to predict the soil fertility level. The soil test report contains the information about macronutrient and micronutrient contents of the given soil. From the soil test reports, the required amount of fertilizer for crop growing is calculated. But it is observed that Madurai district soil contains maximum amount of macronutrient content viz., nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. The farmer support system provides the farmer with effective and smart solution to cultivate the crop yield ensuring a good soil fertility level and minimizing the fertilizer consumption. It has the data pre-processing steps to remove the noisy values in the dataset and then predicts the soil fertility level by using Ensemble classifier model. Fig. 2 explains the process flow of the proposed system. The mapping of the crop to the fertility levels are shown below

Fig. 2. Proposed System

6. METHODOLOGY

Agriculture in India dates back to Indus Valley Civilization. Though 12 to 15% GDP is contributed by agriculture to Indian economy, many small and marginal farmers are under poverty with poor decisions on agriculture practices. Data driven agriculture approach can help the farmers to make right decisions at right time. Data driven approach in agriculture means exploring and learning from the historical field data and taking decisions on what is the crop?, when to sow?, what and how much of fertilizer is required? . These decisions can be combined with traditional agriculture practices to obtain fair outcome. Farmers can be benefitted by adopting this approach significantly. Machine learning algorithms can be used to extract and identify the category and fertility of the soil ,thereby studying in detail the correlation and visualizing the impact of properties with one and deriving the insights and interpretations of the identified results .The proposed steps are

Step 1 Understanding the problem in hand ie identifying appropriate crop to sow in a field by studying the properties of the soil in detail

Step 2: Understanding the domain-specific terminologies, data type, data range, data form. Soil test-based advisories [4] guided to understand the need for each component, its range etc.

Step 3: Preparing the data suitable for study. The dataset had attributes of continuous data type with decimal value, each with its own range. The values beyond the range were considered as outliers and are removed. If a row with a missing value found, then the entire row was deleted, the objective was to workout with the real field data collected from <https://soilhealth.dac.gov.in/>.

Sample No.	pH	EC	OC	N	P	K	S	Zn	Fe	Cu
Block/Mandal: Alanganallur										
Village: ACHCHAMPATTI										
TN640763/2018-19/116159588	7.01000 MAI	0.27000 N	0.35000 L	175.00000 L	63.00000 H	278.00000 M	15.00000 S	1.22000 S	1.26000 D	0.44000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116159753	7.01000 MAI	0.37000 N	0.43000 L	193.00000 L	146.00000 L	119.00000 L	15.00000 S	1.08000 S	1.22000 D	0.88000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116160075	6.80000 SIAC	0.38000 N	0.47000 L	193.00000 L	146.00000 L	292.00000 M	26.00000 S	0.36000 D	1.12000 D	0.76000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116160177	7.23000 MAI	0.35000 N	0.52000 M	210.00000 L	159.00000 L	264.00000 M	14.00000 S	0.90000 S	1.12000 D	1.16000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116160292	7.29000 MAI	0.14000 N	0.35000 L	175.00000 L	185.00000 L	278.00000 M	16.00000 S	0.42000 D	1.22000 D	0.90000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116160513	7.20000 MAI	0.35000 N	0.39000 L	175.00000 L	134.00000 L	242.00000 M	24.00000 S	0.88000 S	1.72000 D	1.22000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116160981	6.90000 SIAC	0.30000 N	0.39000 L	175.00000 L	159.00000 L	306.00000 M	16.00000 S	0.72000 S	1.16000 D	0.66000 S
TN640763/2018-19/116161086	7.01000 MAI	0.34000 N	0.47000 L	193.00000 L	159.00000 L	278.00000 M	24.00000 S	0.66000 S	1.18000 D	0.82000 S

```

Dataset: Village name pH EC OC N P K S Zn Fe \
0 ACHCHAMPATTI 0.82 0.36 0.43 193.0 138.0 264.0 12.0 0.12 2.44
1 ACHCHAMPATTI 7.45 0.31 0.43 193.0 180.0 319.0 14.0 0.06 1.88
2 ACHCHAMPATTI 7.32 0.23 0.23 158.0 125.0 278.0 12.0 0.21 1.28
3 ACHCHAMPATTI 7.21 0.34 0.02 210.0 125.0 288.0 20.0 0.29 1.62
4 ACHCHAMPATTI 6.82 0.29 0.35 175.0 64.0 347.0 22.0 0.88 1.56
5 ACHCHAMPATTI 7.50 0.34 0.43 193.0 66.0 288.0 19.0 1.06 1.34
6 ACHCHAMPATTI 6.85 0.45 0.27 158.0 159.0 264.0 14.0 0.48 1.88
7 ACHCHAMPATTI 7.25 0.30 0.35 175.0 124.0 125.0 16.0 0.28 1.96
8 ACHCHAMPATTI 0.95 0.41 0.35 175.0 122.0 483.0 16.0 1.02 1.18
9 ACHCHAMPATTI 6.80 0.23 0.43 193.0 134.0 125.0 24.0 0.42 1.36

Cu Mn B Fertility Status
0 0.38 1.96 0.780 Low fertile
1 0.30 1.28 1.000 Low fertile
2 0.38 1.80 1.000 Medium Fertile
3 0.46 3.22 1.400 Medium Fertile
4 1.08 2.28 1.200 Low fertile
5 0.40 2.48 0.600 Medium Fertile
6 0.52 2.96 1.400 Medium Fertile
7 0.66 2.36 1.000 Medium Fertile
8 0.72 3.72 0.167 Low fertile
9 0.98 2.82 0.250 Low fertile
    
```

Fig. 3. Raw data (Source : <https://soilhealth.dac.gov.in.>) and Prepared data .

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of Soil Properties

Attributes	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	StdDev
pH	0.06	69	7.618	1.17
EC	0	14	0.356	0.369
OC	0.02	0.5	0.38	0.101
N	0.1	289	167.55	46.266
P	57.25	900	146.83	82.124
K	2.14	1250	383.328	250.725
S	0.001	19329	46.17	294.845
Zn	0.033	28.91	0.889	1.156
Fe	0.025	352	7.642	7.981
Cu	0	10.91	1.229	0.773
Mn	0.118	21.18	4.6	2.5
B	0.008	300	0.538	4.532

Data Visualization

An important task in data preparation was data construction. This task decided the type of algorithm to be carried out to RQ1. Initially, as there was no class label in the dataset, the blind fold proposed method of solution was clustering. But when applied, the clusters were formed considering only one attribute leaving behind others, hence characteristics of members of same cluster was not similar. So, with the guidance of domain expert and soil test interpretation guide the class labels were identified following the rules as given in table 3

IF All the soil constituents have value high then the fertility status is also high ELSE IF five soil constituents have value high and one constituents has Medium/Low value then the fertility status is high ELSE IF four soil constituents have value high and two constituents has Medium/Low value then the fertility status is high ELSE IF three soil constituents have value high and three constituents has Medium/Low value then the fertility status of OC is considered ELSE IF all the soil constituents have value medium then the fertility status is Medium ELSE IF five soil constituents have value Medium and one constituents has High/Low value then the fertility status is Medium ELSE IF three soil constituents have value Medium and three constituents has High/Low value then the fertility status of OC is considered. ELSE IF all the soil constituents have value low then the fertility status is low ELSE IF five soil constituents have value low and one constituent has Medium/High value then the fertility status is low ELSE IF four soil constituents have value low and two constituents has Medium/High value then the fertility status is low ELSE IF three soil constituents have value low and three constituents have Medium/High value then the fertility status of OC is considered.
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Table 3. Soil Fertility prediction rules.

Step 4 : Choosing the most contributing and relevant attributes by discarding the irrelevant attributes from the database is the major objective of feature selection.

The benefits of performing feature selection before modeling the data are:

- Avoid Over fitting: Less redundant data gives performance boost to the model and results in less opportunity to make decisions based on noise
- Reduces Training Time: Less data means that algorithms train faster

Fisher Score Feature Selection algorithm selects each feature independently in accordance based on their scores under the Fisher criterion, which eventually leads to a subset of the most representative individual

Feature selection using the Fisher score algorithm results in a list of attributes that are ranked by their importance.

The score of the i^{th} feature S_i will be calculated by Fisher Score using

$$S_i = \frac{\sum n_j (\mu_{ij} - \mu_i)^2}{\sum n_j \cdot \rho^2_{ij}}$$

where

- μ_{ij} - mean of the i^{th} feature in the j^{th} class,
- ρ_{ij} - variance of the i^{th} feature in the j^{th} class
- n_j - number of instances in the j^{th} class
- μ_i is the mean of the i^{th} feature.

Here, we have computed the chi-squared stats between each non negative feature and the target class. Given the input, the target variable is separated from the rest of the input variables, the obtained P-value is sorted in descending order, Smaller the p-value, more significant the feature is to predict the target value. The significant features in 5th and 6th which is OC, N are identified.

```

fisher_score = chi2(X_train, y_train)
fisher_score

array([[2.35880481e+01, 1.28535141e+02, 1.88563269e-01, 4.76327878e+02,
        8.75873845e+02, 4.58888894e+04, 2.52282630e+03, 1.87243957e+01,
        7.21961795e+00, 1.18449248e-01, 2.23865199e+00]),
       array([7.88916632e-006, 5.78879945e-027, 9.23779674e-081, 3.68737423e-184,
        9.55276253e-191, 0.00000000e+000, 0.00000000e+000, 4.69858546e-083,
        2.78578149e-082, 3.99599707e-083, 3.27888398e-081]))

2          9.237797e-81
18         3.278884e-81
8          2.785781e-82
7          4.698585e-83
9          3.995998e-83
0          7.889167e-86
1          6.788799e-27
3          3.687374e-184
4          9.552763e-191
6          0.000000e+00
5          0.000000e+00
dtype: float64

p_values = pd.Series(fisher_score[1])
p_values.sort_values(ascending=False)

```

Fig. 4. Feature Selection Using Chi-Square Test and p-Value Sorting

Step 5 Modelling is to combine the insight from all previous analysis to determine which action to take in a current problem or decision. This data driven approach helps to achieve the Research Question 1 and 2 to greater extend taking the advantage of Classification models. Classification Algorithms targets at building a function taking input feature vector “A” and predicting its outcome “B”.

Classification model: Classification is a supervised learning method used in various re-

search fields whose goal is to classify a large set of objects into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. A classification model tries to predict the target class label/category of a new observation, on the basis of analysis from training dataset containing observations and whose categories membership is known.

Classification is a two-phase process such as:

- 1. Learning phase:** To develop a model by applying a classification algorithm training data set is the first step.
- 2. Classification phase:** To test the constructed model on test data and estimating the accuracy of the classification rules are done.

Fig. 5. General Framework of Classification Model

The existing algorithms to solve this data driven problem are as follows:

KNN: The k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a straightforward supervised learning technique used to solve classification problems. In this approach, each feature of the training data is treated as a dimension in a multi-dimensional space. The value of a feature for an observation is its coordinate in that dimension, forming a set of points in this space. The similarity between two points is measured by their distance in this space using a specified metric. The algorithm identifies the k nearest data points in the training set to classify a new observation and assigns the most frequent class among these neighbours to the latest observation.

Random Forest is a versatile and user-friendly machine learning algorithm that generally delivers strong results even without extensive hyperparameter tuning. It is commonly used for both classification and regression tasks. In regression problems, the algorithm can utilize Mean Squared Error (MSE) to determine the optimal splits at each node in the decision trees that make up the forest. This method helps in improving prediction accuracy by aggregating the predictions of multiple decision trees, thus enhancing overall model performance and robustness.

Decision Tree provides a highly effective framework within which options can be laid out and the possible results of choosing those options can be investigated. ID3, CART, c4.5 are some of the algorithms used in decision trees. We will be calculating impurity, entropy and information gain for decision tree construction .

ADA Boost focuses on training upon misclassified observations. Alters the distribution of the training dataset to increase weights on sample observations that are difficult to classify. The final prediction is based on a majority vote of the weak learners' predictions weighted by their individual accuracy.

Gradient Boost trains learners based upon minimizing the loss function of a learner (i.e., training on the residuals of the model). Weak learners are decision trees constructed in a greedy manner with split points based on purity scores (i.e., Gini, minimize loss). Thus, larger trees can be used with around 4 to 8 levels. Learners should still remain weak and so they should be constrained (i.e., the maximum number of layers, nodes, splits, leaf nodes). All the learners have equal weights in the case of gradient boosting. The weight is usually set as the learning rate which is small in magnitude

A novel well-designed model is used to classify the soil fertility level in the proposed work and help to decide the farmers what crop to sow? and what fertilizer to use? Soil test report contains the information about Chemical Properties such as pH, EC, OC, Macronutrient and Micronutrient contents of the given soil. From the soil test reports, it is observed that distribution of fertility from low to high is widely spread in 13 blocks of Madurai region. The maximum, minimum, mean and standard deviation of each soil composition is listed below in Table 2.

Proposed Ensemble classifier algorithm

Let the given input space $A \subseteq B$ and f be the feature vectors and a finite set of classification Target labels $T = \{1, \dots, m\}$, a classifier is a (total) function $C : A \rightarrow \wp^+(T)$, where $\wp^+(T)$ denotes the set of nonempty subsets of T , which assigns at least one label to every input in A . The application S of C on a set $Y \subseteq A$ of inputs is simply denoted by $C(Y)$, $x \in Y \rightarrow C(x)$. The proposed Ensemble classifier model follow the learning principle based on scoring and voting schemes. An ensemble decision-tree based classifier is defined as a classifier that combines multiple trained decision-tree classifiers to produce a single final

classification. Score functions are the output of a learning algorithm on some training dataset $D \subseteq A \times T$ which explores a hypothesis space of functions and returns a best fit for the training set D . Let the set of labels having maximal score for some function score: $A \rightarrow B^{|T|}$, i.e. $C(x) = \{i \in T \mid \forall j. \text{score}(x)_i \geq \text{score}(x)_j\}$. [9] . A decision tree DT is a finite branching structure where: (i) each internal node N has a finite set of successor nodes $S(N)$ and is endowed with a decision rule called split condition, $\text{split } n : A \rightarrow S(N)$ on input vectors, so that the branches outgoing from N represent the possible outputs of $\text{split } n$; (ii) the set of leaves of p is denoted by $L(p)$ and each leaf stores some information on labels which is used for a final decision/classification, so that a path from the root to a leaf represents a classification rule. Leaves typically store tuples in $B^{|T|}$ which play the role of output for

a decision tree, which therefore induces a score function $s: A \rightarrow B |T|$ for input samples in A , also denoted by score $s(x)$.

To improve accuracy and generalizability, ensemble methods allow to combine several constituent learning models. For score-based classifiers, every classifier is fed with the same input and computes its own score function, so that scores from multiple classifiers are then combined into a single score typically by applying some voting mechanism. The two most common voting schemes are: (Max): each constituent classifier contributes with a label-indexed tuple of either 1 (for labels with maximal score) or 0 (non-maximal scores), and then votes are added; (Average): each constituent classifier computes a label-indexed tuple of scores in $[0, 1]$, and then the average score for each label is computed.

Based on the composition of observed vector features such chemical properties and macro –micro nutrients, the class - soil fertility is classified automatically with built Classification model. With the fertility status known, the required amount of fertilizer for crop growing ie Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium is calculated accordingly. This evidences the RQ2, because usage of appropriate amount of fertilizer to land helps to sustain the soil health eradicating soil compaction and aggravating acidification. Hence, only data driven farming can promote sustainable agriculture and save soil fertility. process response is sent back to the user's with useful recommendations with crop details and fertility levels.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A comprehensive soil health dataset was compiled from the Soil Health Card portal, incorporating 20,000 soil samples from 13 blocks in Madurai district. The dataset featured 14 key attributes, including pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Organic Carbon (OC), Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K), along with essential micronutrients. These attributes facilitated the classification of soil fertility into Low, Medium, and High categories. To enhance model reliability, data preprocessing steps such as outlier removal, missing value handling, and normalization were applied. Feature selection using Fisher Score and Chi-Square analysis identified OC, N, and P as the most influential factors in determining soil fertility. Fig 6 shows the correlation between the attributes. An ensemble classification system was implemented using multiple machine learning models, including Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naïve Bayes (NB), AdaBoost (AB), Gradient Boosting (GB), LightGBM (LGBM), and a Voting Classifier. Random Forest emerged as the most effective model, achieving 99.44% accuracy and an AUC of 0.83 for low fertility prediction. Decision Tree, LightGBM, and Voting Classifier achieved the highest accuracy of 99.89%. Gradient Boosting and Random Forest demonstrated stable and reliable performance. KNN and Naïve Bayes performed poorly, making them unsuitable for fertility classification. AdaBoost showed moderate effectiveness with 79.77% accuracy but was outperformed by ensemble methods.

The given ROC curve represents the performance of a classifiers in distinguishing different fertility levels (Low, Medium, and High) against the rest. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) values indicate the model’s effectiveness in classification.

The Fig 7 ROC analysis suggests that the decision tree classifier performs poorly in distinguishing between fertility levels. The AUC values for Low Fertile vs. Rest (0.50), Medium Fertile vs. Rest (0.37), and High Fertile vs. Rest (0.40) indicate a classification performance close to or below random guessing (AUC = 0.50). The Low Fertile vs. Rest category achieves an AUC of 0.50, implying that the model does not provide any discriminatory power beyond random chance. Meanwhile, the Medium and High Fertile classifications have AUC values significantly below 0.50, suggesting that the model may be making incorrect classifications more often than expected. These findings highlight the need for a more sophisticated model or additional feature engineering to improve classification accuracy. This study successfully developed a highly accurate ensemble classification system to predict soil fertility based on pH, macronutrients, and other key soil attributes. The Random Forest model achieved the highest AUC (0.83), making it the most reliable classifier.

Fig. 6. Correlation Matrix

Fig. 7. Machine Learning Models ROC Curve

Fertility Classification and Crop Recommendation

The Decision Support System (DSS) categorized soil samples into fertility levels and provided tailored crop and fertilizer recommendations based on soil nutrient content. This approach ensured optimized fertilizer application and enhanced agricultural productivity. A mobile application was developed to provide real-time soil health insights with the following functionalities:

1. Farmers can input soil test data to receive predictions on fertility levels and recommendations for suitable crops .
2. A GIS-based soil fertility mapping tool was integrated, enabling farmers to visualize nutrient distribution trends across the Madurai district.

3. Registered farmers receive automated SMS alerts with Fertility level predictions and Recommended crops for their location

Fig. 8 Crop Prediction App

Fig. 9. GIS- based soil fertility mapping

your region (அச்சம்பட்டி)
and soil pH (7.45), the
recommended crops are:
['பருப்பு', 'காய்கறிகள்'].
Ideal pH: 7.45.

on your region
(சின்னைலந்தைக்குளம்)
and soil pH (7.81), the
recommended crops are:
['பருப்பு', 'காய்கறிகள்'].
Ideal pH: 7.81.

CONCLUSION

This study presents a data-driven approach to soil fertility classification based on pH, macronutrients, and other key soil attributes using an ensemble machine learning model, which significantly improves the accuracy of soil health assessment. The study demonstrates that integrating machine learning techniques, such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, with soil health data can effectively classify fertility levels and assist in crop selection and fertilizer recommendations. The Decision Support System (DSS) developed in this study serves as a crucial step toward precision agriculture, offering real-time insights to farmers through a mobile application and GIS-based fertility mapping. The findings contribute to the growing field of agricultural informatics by bridging the gap between data science and sustainable farming practices. While the proposed model demonstrates high accuracy, future research can focus on expanding data sources such as integrating satellite imagery, climate data, and remote sensing technologies to improve prediction accuracy. Implementing self-learning AI models that evolve with new soil samples and environmental changes, improving long-term reliability. Extending the study beyond Madurai district to other agricultural regions with diverse soil compositions, enabling a more generalized and scalable model.

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